

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR RECOVERY OF PRESSURE AND NON-PRESSURE PIPING

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada trubalarni reabilitatsiya qilishning xandakli usullari, usullarning mazmun-mohiyati, ularning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tarmoqlarni qayta tiklashning bu usullaridan foydalanish xarajatlarni va atrof-muhit xavfsizligini minimallashtirish imkoniyatini beradi, xalq uchun noqulaylik tug'dirmasdan, buzilgan yoki o'zgacha vaziyatda aloqa bo'limlarini tezlik bilan almashtirish imkoniyatini beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Innovative technologies, recovery, pressure, non-pressure, spiral-wound, sewerage pipelines, new pipe.

Reforming and updating housing and communal services is unthinkable without the technological modernization of utility pipeline networks. Statistical data confirm the critical degree (from 65% to 95%) of the deterioration of water supply and sewerage pipelines in many large and small cities of our country.

Traditional trench methods of pipeline rehabilitation are associated with a large amount of excavation, strengthening the walls of trenches, blocking traffic flows, destruction of road surfaces, damage to green plantations, violation of infrastructure, which entails large material costs for restoration work, and also interference in the usual life of megacities. That is why the LinerTech company uses modern trenchless methods of restoration (rehabilitation) of pipelines. The use of spiral-wound technology, pulling a new pipe inside an old or hardened sleeve (stocking), with which excavation is absent or reduced to minimum. New technologies are the most efficient and a cost-effective solution to the problem of restoration and reconstruction of utility engineering networks in modern conditions, while maintaining comfort and the environment.

Let us consider in more detail the trenchless methods of sanitation of pipelines.

1. Spiral-wound technology for the rehabilitation of pipelines SWP. It is used to restore free-flow pipelines with a diameter of 200 to 3000 mm. Spiral wound technology is a recovery method for pipelines by winding the PVC profile in a spiral inside existing pipe (fig. 1). During the winding process, a new pipe is formed, which is completely self-supporting.

Fig.1 General view of the work

Spiral-wound technology is used for sanitation non-pressure networks:

- sewers;
- storm pipelines;
- industrial networks;

To date, spiral winding is one of the most optimal solutions in dense urban areas. Let us analyze in more detail the essence of the method and its distinctive features.

1. Before the start of the coiling process, telediagnosics of the inner surface of the pipe to be restored is carried out. In the process of telediagnosics, blockages, collapses are detected vault and other damage to the old pipe.

2. Then the inner surface of the pipe is cleared of blockages, deposits and deposits with a hydrodynamic washing machine.

2. The winding machine is lowered to the bottom of a standard well and adjusted to the appropriate pipe diameter.

The PVC profile enters the machine from a reel located on the surface of the well. The spiral winding machine forms a new PVC profile pipe in the old pipe. Spiral process winding continues until the new pipe reaches the end of the restored section of the pipe (Fig. 2).

Fig.2 Equipment installation

Stopping or pumping wastewater is not required, as well as construction of a bypass line, work is carried out according to the current flow. The construction site occupies a minimum of ground surface. In the immediate vicinity of the well hatch, a coil with a profile is placed. PVC profile with lock connection along the entire length, is fed from the reel to the winding machine, the equipment snaps the lock and pushes the wound pipe of smaller diameter along the entire length of the sanitized area. Next, the so-called expansion process takes place, after which the new pipe fits snugly against the walls of the old pipe, or the annular space is filled with an exclusive backfilling solution, which has increased fluidity and fast setting times.

The new pipe has a smooth surface, thereby increasing the throughput of the new pipe, and the new pipe takes on all the bearing load.

The three-component bonding system eliminates the possibility of linear shifts. The ends of the casing pipe from both cleaning chambers (wells) are hermetically connected and fixed with a special solution to connect the casing pipe to the main pipe.

The final stage is a repeated television inspection to check the quality of the work performed. After restoration, we get a self-supporting pipe with improved hydraulic characteristics, minimal narrowing of the diameter and a service life of more than 50 years.

3. SANIVAR technology for the restoration of pressure networks with a diameter of 80 to 500 mm.

The technology is based on the use of a round woven sleeve - 100% polyester fiber hose coated on both sides polyethylene or high temperature polyurethane. SANIVAR technology (Fig. 3) is used to restore pressure networks:

- plumbing;
- - gas pipeline;
- - oil pipelines, etc.

Fig. 3. View of a stocking with a socket connection

The pipeline is cleaned mechanically or hydrodynamically. Next, a television inspection is carried out to make sure that the pipe is ready for sanitation. Into the prepared pipe with a winch at a speed 3-5 m/min stretches a polymer sleeve. When the sleeve reaches final position, it is straightened with air supplied under pressure of 1 bar to give the sleeve a round shape.

To secure the sleeve, a coupling connection is installed on both sides. The peculiarity of this technology lies in the fact that sanitation passes without the use of resins and glue, which allows you to work with this method in the shortest possible time.

Conclusions on the use of trenchless methods for the restoration of engineering networks:

Possibility to avoid earthworks in case of need for restoration (overhaul) of certain utility networks, allows you to achieve significant savings time and money.

Such work is allowed to be carried out by teams of high qualifications, but the minimum number, without the use of overall equipment and without even opening a warrant for earthworks.

As a result, the terms of work are reduced to the minimum, and the Customer does not need to worry about the removal, disposal or temporary placement of soil, restoration road and sidewalk coverings, disturbed urban improvement, subsequent landscaping. Other advantages of using trenchless methods:

- the ability to restore communications located in unstable soils;
- increasing the capacity of the new pipeline;
- no damage to buildings, gardens, parks and other urban infrastructure;
- the possibility of using trenchless methods, including when working in hard-to-reach areas;
- minimization of risks of damage to neighboring engineering communications (cables or pipes);
- no interference with city traffic;

These methods of rehabilitation of networks do not interfere with the urban cycle, which allows you to quickly replace faulty or emergency sections of communications without creating discomfort for residents.

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